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OVERVIEW OF THE SITUATION FACED BY INTERNATIONAL STUDENTS IN UKRAINE

During the year Ukraine hosts foreign students from 134 countries mostly from Asia and Africa. Most of them study in universities of Kharkiv, Kyiv, Odesa [1]. Almost 40% of all international students come to Ukraine to study medicine. Foreign students receive education in the universities of Ukraine on fee paid basis. This article contains a general overview of the most common problems faced by international students in Ukraine, but it doesn't lay a claim to be exhaustive, comprehensive or a generalization. Since Soviet period Ukraine has been an attractive destination for foreign students. Foreign students, being often misinformed, choose Ukraine as a place of their graduate or post-graduate studies. Prevailing majority of them prefer studying in Ukraine because of the relatively low university fees and cost of living (particularly in comparison to EU and North America). Another reason is a good reputation of Ukrainian universities stemming from Soviet times. Usually they follow advices and references of older relatives or family friends of many of the current foreign students who obtained their university degrees in Soviet Union. Unfortunately there are not so much reliable sources of information about educational opportunities in Ukraine available for foreign students that is why they often are misinformed about realities of Ukrainian system of education, current valid prices for education for foreigners, dormitory conditions, as well as the level of racial intolerance in some regions. Some but not all of the recruiting agents play the significant role in misinforming and misleading foreigners. They provide students with deliberately untruthful information about the quality of education, conditions of living and prices, promoting Ukraine as a safest state for foreigners. The main sources of information about conditions of study in Ukraine available to foreign students include: Internet resources, including web-sites of recruiting companies, agencies assisting with admissions, university web-sites etc [2].

Often, foreign students are not allowed to cross the border and kept in the terminal for a long time (sometimes even several days), even though despite the fact that their documents are in perfect order. Usually foreign students are not informed of the actual reasons behind these practices, which also include the university representatives' failure to confirm the status of the student to border-guards in a timely manner.

Physical safety remains one of the principal concerns of students. Students in Kharkiv have expressed concerns about having to carry not only their passport, but a dormitory pass, student ID, and tenancy contracts for those not living in the dorm. In case they do not present some of these documents when stopped by policemen, they are required to pay “a fine” immediately, at the place where they’re being checked. Ethnic profiling in Kharkiv is evident, in particular on the territory of metro, and appears to be a regular practice for law enforcement in the city.

As a rule, foreign students study apart from Ukrainian students, as well as they live in separate dormitories in some universities. Moreover, there were reported incidents where members of university administration instructed local students not to interact with international students who lived in the same dormitory with them because “foreigners bring diseases”.

References:

1. <https://studyinukraine.gov.ua/en/life-in-ukraine/international-students-in-ukraine/>
2. <https://wenr.wes.org/2019/06/education-in-ukraine>

ОГЛЯД СИТУАЦІЇ, З ЯКОЮ ЗІТКНУЛИСЯ МІЖНАРОДНІ СТУДЕНТИ В УКРАЇНІ

Іноземні студенти отримують освіту в університетах України на платній основі. Ця стаття містить загальний огляд найпоширеніших проблем, з якими стикаються іноземні студенти в Україні. Зазвичай вони дотримуються порад та рекомендацій старших родичів чи друзів сімей багатьох сучасних іноземних студентів, які здобули вищу освіту в Радянському Союзі. На жаль, для іноземних студентів доступні не стільки надійні джерела інформації про можливості навчання в Україні, тому їх часто дезінформують про реалії української системи навчання, чинні діючі ціни на освіту для іноземців, умови проживання в гуртожитках, а також рівень расової нетерпимості в деяких регіонах.

Ключові слова: освіта, проблеми іноземних студентів, Україна.

OVERVIEW OF THE SITUATION FACED BY INTERNATIONAL STUDENTS IN UKRAINE

International students study at Ukrainian universities on a paid basis. This article provides an overview of the most common problems faced by foreign students in Ukraine. They usually follow the advice and recommendations of senior relatives or family friends of many modern foreign students who graduated in the Soviet Union. Unfortunately, foreign students have less reliable sources of information on study opportunities in Ukraine, so they are often misinformed about the realities of the Ukrainian education system, current prices for education for foreigners, living conditions in dormitories, and the level of racial intolerance in some regions.

***Key words:** education, problems of foreign students, Ukraine*